

Digital Twin Interface for Facility Management Using openBIM Standards

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Abstract

This thesis explores the enhancement of facility management processes by integrating Building Information Modelling (BIM) into existing systems by the creation of a web-based interface for a Digital Twin. The project ensures interoperability across platforms by using openBIM standards and Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), enabling seamless integration and manipulation of data directly within a web-based interface. It facilitates the extraction and manipulation of information from the IFC model, retrieval of real-time sensor data, and linking of results to specific equipment and spaces. This approach aims to improve facility management through more efficient visualization of sensor data. The prototype demonstrates how real-time sensor data can be integrated with the BIM model, allowing facility managers to monitor temperature, humidity, occupancy data, and other thermal metrics in specific spaces. This innovation provides a more intuitive platform for identifying potential issues, monitoring occupancy, and optimizing building performance. Additionally, the interface integrates Power BI dashboards to display advanced analytics, offering facility managers detailed

and customizable insights into building operations. Future improvements include the capability to analyze data over specific periods, implement predictive analytics, and enable direct equipment control, which would further enhance decision-making and expand the system's applicability to a broader range of facility management scenarios.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

https://youtu.be/_Ckp-RsMDoU

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